

Temple of the Rock/Temple HH1 (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla)

also known as “Kura’s Temple in the Lower Town South-East”

By Maura Sala, Faculty of Theology of Lugano – Università della Svizzera italiana

Entry tags: Temple, Ritual Deposit, Religious Group, north-western inner Syria, Early Bronze Age, Early Bronze IVA (mature Early Syrian Period), Near East, Ancient Syrian Religion, Religious Place, Archaeological monument, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, northern Levant, Semitic, East Semitic, Language, Afro-Asiatic, Eblaite

The Temple of the Rock (Temple HH1) is a monumental temple building erected in the ancient city of Ebla (present-day Tell Mardikh). It dates back to the age of the Royal Archives of the great Early Syrian town, c. 2400–2300 BCE (in the traditional conventional chronology), that is the Early Bronze IVA of north-western inland Syria chronology. It is so far the only identified cult building belonging to the age of the Archives, along with the Red Temple on the Acropolis: together with the Archive’ texts, these two sanctuaries offer crucial insights into the religious phenomena in Ebla and Syria in the mature Early Syrian Period; and provide evidence of the unity and specificity of the religious architectural tradition of inland Syria in the central part of the third millennium BCE, when the in-antis temple model spreads. The temple is located in the south-eastern Lower Town, west of the mighty Middle Bronze Age ramparts and not far from the south-east city-gate (the Steppe Gate). It occupied a peripheral position in the mature Early Syrian urban layout. In this sector (Area HH), a huge sacred area developed from the mid-third millennium BCE and remained continuously in use up to the final destruction of the Middle Bronze Age city around 1600 BCE. Five superimposed temples were excavated. The Temple of the Rock was the first building to be erected. We can identify this cult building with the Temple of Kura which stood close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura: the place where, according to the text of the “Ritual of Kingship”, the elaborate ritual of the renewal of kingship began with the queen entering the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the town wall. A series of ceremonial acts and pilgrimages performed together by the king and queen followed, until the royal couple entered the second Temple of Kura within the SA.ZA on the Acropolis (now identified with the Red Temple) and concluded the ritual. The temple is an imposing building (28 m long and some 21.50 m wide), facing east, still more than 3.50 m high, which featured a façade with projecting antae, a latitudinal cella, and a deep vestibule of the same size as the cella. The temple belongs to the in antis typology, well attested in the Syro-Levantine religious architecture from the mid-third millennium BCE, and exhibits strong similarities with the Red Temple on the Acropolis for its typology, size, and proportions. However, in the Temple of the Rock the cella (L.9190), to the west, and the vestibule (L.9495), to the east, had the same size (a peculiar feature not found elsewhere): both are moderately broad rooms, wider (10 m) than long (8.30 m). Based on the considerable thickness of the outer walls (about 6 m), the temple may have risen to over 15 m. It had stone foundations, mostly great basalt and limestone blocks of an average height of 0.80/1.20 m, and a mudbrick superstructure; the bricks belong to the rectangular type used in the mature Early Syrian Period, that is, 0.60 by 0.40 by 0.10 m. The building was founded directly over a low emergence of the bedrock (hence its name), which was not completely levelled at this point: the irregularities and cavities in the rock were left visible in the floor of the cella and the vestibule, as they allegedly had a special meaning for the builders. In particular, the cella was built in a spot marked by a large ellipsoid cavity with three wells (P.9713, P.9717, P.9719), descending into the depths of the rock to the water-bearing stratum. These wells had probably been springs with special mythical, natural, or historical significance, presumably as the place from which the subterranean waters over which Kura presided sprang to the surface, or as the place from which the mythical divine residence of the lord of the pantheon could be reached. Therefore,

the cavity and the wells would have been the reason which supported the choice of this peripheral site for the erection of the temple, both for the physical nature of the place (presence of fresh water) and for its mythical association with the residence of a great god in the abyss below. The temple was destroyed at the end of the Early Bronze IVA, around 2300 BCE, when the whole city of the Royal Palace of the Archives was sacked and destroyed. It then underwent a sort of termination ritual, including the clearing of nearly all traces of destruction, the deposition of a great amount of fine vessels (more than 200) in two of the wells (P.9717 and P.9719) inside the cavity in the cella, and the ritual sealing of the cella and antecella by means of several mudbrick courses, at the beginning of the Early Bronze IVB. The inner space of the temple was, finally, filled up with a 3.5 m high filling of crushed limestone and chalky pebble, carried out to make the place inviolable after its abandonment. The location of the remains of the temple (which formed a small hillock), however, maintained its sacrality for the inhabitants of the later cities. In fact, during an advanced phase of the Early Bronze IVB (late Early Syrian Period) two adjacent temples were built to the east, in the open space in front of the oldest temple: Temple HH4 and Temple HH5; while two large, superimposed tripartite temples (HH3 and HH2) would have been erected in the same spot during the Middle Bronze Age (Old Syrian Period) (Matthiae 2021, pp. 65–83, 297–300).

Date Range: 2400 BCE - 2300 BCE

Region: Ebla/Tell Mardikh

Region tags: North-western inner Syria, Syria

The archaeological site of Tell Mardikh, ancient Ebla, is located in upper inner Syria, 55 km south of Aleppo. The site has an extension of 56 hectares. It has been continuously excavated by an archaeological expedition of the Sapienza University of Rome between 1964 and 2010, for 47 uninterrupted campaigns, which brought to light the large fortified urban settlements of the Early Bronze and Middle Bronze Ages (mature/late Early Syrian Period and Old Syrian Period).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Matthiae, P. 2021. *Ebla : Archaeology and History* . London / New York : Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- Source 2: Matthiae, P. 2009. Temples and Queens at Ebla. Recent Discoveries in a Syrian Metropolis between Mesopotamia, Egypt and the Levant, in *Interconnections in the Eastern Mediterranean. Lebanon in the Bronze and Iron Ages. Proceedings of the International Symposium Beirut 2008 (BAAL, Hors-Série VI)*. Beirut: Ministère de la Culture, Direction Générale des Antiquités, pp. 117-139.
- Source 3: Matthiae, P. 2010. Recent Excavations at Ebla, 2006-2007, in in P. Matthiae et al. (eds.), *Proceedings of the 6th International Congress of the Archaeology of the Ancient Near East, 5 May - 10 May 2008, »Sapienza«, Università Di Roma. Volume 2, Excavations, Surveys and Restorations: Reports on*

Recent Field Archaeology in the Near East. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2010, pp. 3-26.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2004-2007

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Ebla (MAIS)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: The temple was built in a spot marked by a broad ellipsoid cavity in the bedrock (L.9714), with three wells (P.9713, P.9717, P.9719) descending deep to the water-bearing stratum

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: However, the temple was completely independent of the adjacent buildings and had no additional rooms.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: It was located close to the town wall and the south-east city-gate, the so-called Gate of Kura of the Early Syrian town.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: 28 m long and some 21.50 m wide

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: A broad ellipsoid cavity in the bedrock (L.9714), with three wells (P.9713, P.9717, P.9719) descending deep to the water-bearing stratum

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Political

Notes: The Temple of the Rock has presumably to be identified with the Temple of Kura which stood close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura of the Early Syrian town: the place where, according to the text of the "Ritual of Kingship", the elaborate ritual of the kingship began with the queen entering the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the town wall.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The Temple of the Rock was destroyed at the same time as the whole settlement of the age of the Royal Archives, at the end of Early Bronze IVA, around 2300 BCE.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità* 15 (2009): 43–83.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: The temple was presumably burnt as a result of the destruction which brought to an end the city of the Royal Palace of the Archives around 2300 BCE. It was then accurately cleaned of nearly all traces of destruction, and ritually sealed with superimposed courses of mud-bricks and with an intentional filling of crushed limestone and chalky pebble, to make the place inviolable after its abandonment.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

Notes: The conquest and devastation possibly carried out by Sargon of Akkad around 2300 BC.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: However, the location of the remains of the temple (which formed a small hillock) maintained its sacrality for the inhabitants of the later cities. In fact, during an advanced phase of the Early Bronze IVB (late Early Syrian Period) two adjacent temples were built to the east, in the open space in front of the oldest temple: Temple HH4 and Temple HH5; while two large, superimposed tripartite temples (HH3 and HH2) would have been erected in the same spot during the Middle Bronze Age (Old Syrian Period) .

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Probably God Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon, probably the lord of fresh waters who resided in the abyss. The Eblaite god Kura was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions (he may be considered as an archaic analogue of El, distinguished by chthonic rather than celestial features); he was patron god of the city and the protector of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. The Temple of the Rock was presumably considered the place from which the subterranean waters over which Kura presided sprang to the surface, or the place from which the mythical divine residence of the lord of the pantheon could be reached.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: It is likely that the Kura's Temple in the Lower Town, identified with the Temple of the Rock, was believed to have been erected by the god Kura himself as his own residence or as a gateway to his mythical seat.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Mythical, natural and/or historical reasons: both for the physical nature of the place (presence of fresh water) and for its mythical association with the residence of a great god in the abyss below.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 600

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 15

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Notes: The building had stone foundations, mostly great basalt and limestone blocks of an average height of some 0.80/1.20 m, and a mudbrick superstructure; the bricks were the rectangular type used in the mature Early Syrian Period, that is, 0.60 by 0.40 by 0.10 m

↳ Earth
– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: Foundations, mostly great basalt and limestone blocks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Probably god Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon in the age of the Archives. He was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss. He was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions, patron god of the city and protector of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. He remains the most obscure deity appearing in the written documents from the third quarter of the third millennium BCE. However, he does not seem to differ much from the type of Dagan of Tuttul, and he also had paternal and celestial attributions similar to those which, in the second millennium BCE, must have belonged to El (in the pantheon of Ugarit). Kura's (and Ishkhara's) prominence in the city of the Archives points to archaic character of the religious system of Early Syrian Ebla and reveals a situation preceding the full establishment of gods like Adda/Hadad and Ashtar/Ishtar in Syria and Upper Mesopotamia. According to written sources, two temples closely associated with the kingship were erected to Kura: a temple, close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura, where, at the beginning of the celebrations for the renewal of kingship, the queen entered the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the city walls; a second temple within the SAZA, the central palatine administrative complex, where the elaborate ritual of kingship concluded with the enthronement of the royal couple at the end of a pilgrimage to the shrines of their deified ancestors. The Temple of the Rock which stood by the Steppe Gate (to be identified with the Early Syrian gate described as the Kura Gate in the Archive's texts) was in all probability the first of the two temples dedicated to Kura, where the ritual of kingship began.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura possibly had celestial attributions.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Ritual of Kingship. The Temple of the Rock was presumably the Temple of Kura which stood close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura of the Early Syrian town: the place where, according to the text of the "Ritual of Kingship", the elaborate ritual of the renewal of kingship began with the queen entering the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the town wall.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

By all the community

– Field doesn't know

By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla, the elite members and the priesthood.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità* 15 (2009): 43-83.